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यथा यथा हि पुरुषः शास्त्रं समधिगच्छति ।
तथा तथा विजानाति विज्ञानञ्चास्य रोचते ॥

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I
J
P
S

18. *Kamlesh Gupta*
Gram Sabha : A step towards Self Governance 209-214
19. *Rajbir Singh Dalal*
Problems of Skilled Youths : Prospects and Challenges 215-226
20. *Ruby Kumari*
India's Nuclear Weapon Programme Present Capabilities 227-238
21. *Rajkumar Singh*
Relevance of Saarc in South Asian Context 239-248
22. *Bhupinder Singh*
Punjab Assembly Elections 2007 : An Analysis 249-260
23. *Muzaffar Assadi*
Karnataka Assembly Election : BJP's Victory and Trend Towards 3 Party System 261-271
24. *R. V.R. Murthy*
Andaman and Nicobar Command (ANC) : Friendship across of Seas 273-282

Book-Reviews

25. *Sushma Yadav*
Politics of Inclusion: Caste, Minorities and Affirmative Action by Zoya Hasan, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2009, pp.302, Rs.675/- 283-287
26. *Abhay Vikram Singh*
Consumer Rights in Service Sector Edited by V.N.Viswanathan, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi,2008,pp. 234, Price: Rs.600/- 288-290
27. *Archana Kumari*
Society, Politics and Development in North East India by Ashok Kumar Ray and Satyabrata Chakraborty, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi, 2008, pp. 361, Price: Rs.900/- 290-292
28. *Bina Rai*
Women in Governance in Tripura by Bhola Nath Ghosh, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi, 2008, pp. 209, Price: Rs.500/- 292-294
29. *Deeptima Shukla*
India-Uganda Relations: A New Model For South-South Cooperation by Surya Narain Yadav, Global Vision Publishing House, New Delhi, 2008, pp. 276, Price: Rs.690/- 295-297
30. *Dibyendu Dasgupta*
Mizoram: Dimensions and Perspective Edited by Jagdish K.Patnaik, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi,2008,pp. 475, Price: Rs.1200/- 297-299
31. *J.K. Mishra*
Women Academics in Higher Education by Niranjan Pani and Goutami Das, Mahamaya Publishing House, New Delhi,2008, pp. 229, Price: Rs.650/- 300-301
32. *Tirranjan Raj*
Human Rights Challenges of 21st Century Edited by V.N.Viswanathan, Kalpaz Publications, Delhi, 2008, pp. 304, Price: Rs.720/- 302-303

of sustainable development in northeastern India found that the macro context of development created regional imbalances and skewed income distribution in the developing countries. Prof. Nixon Singh made a case for the promotion of tourism in northeastern region of India in view of growing importance of this sector in economic growth and revenue generation. Surojit Sengupta studied the urbanization dynamics in Meghalaya whereas Prof. Malabika Dasgupta in the next chapter found low urbanization among the tribal population in Tripura.

Prof. Paulavi Das in the chapter entitled "Women Development and sex Ratio: Treading between North and North East India" raised the issue of women development and the skewed sex-ratio in the two social contexts of the North and the North-East India. In the next chapter Prof. Jahita Begum and M. Vakkil have shown how ICT can be instrumental in empowerment of women. Prof. Kaustav Lahiri in the last chapter dealt with sustainable development with Ecological Dimension of Sustainability and focuses on the overall viability and health of ecological systems in terms of a comprehensive, multi-scale, dynamic, hierarchical measure of 'Resilience', 'Vigor' and 'Organization' in the context of North-East India. The issues and concerns raised by the authors of these articles are of immense significance in the specific socio-economic and development context of North-East India. The contents of this book are well researched and thought provoking. This book has raised and addressed multi-dimensional issues of society, culture and development in the northeastern region. Apart of imparting academic values this book gives food for thought to the development thinkers and the policy-makers.

Archana Kumari

BOOK REVIEW

Women in Governance in Tripura by Bhola Nath Ghosh, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi, 2008, pp. 209, Price: Rs.500

Panchayati system in Tripura has progressed a long way from its traditional to present day structure. Before Tripura merged with the Indian Union in 1949, it was a princely state. There were traditional village level institutions based on traditional customs, which took important decisions in matters pertaining to tribal communities and to dispute among their members. But these institutions could hardly be described as democratic, depending as they did on the social legitimacy conferred on them by the existing power structure and social order. Women were denied the right to participate in these village councils. The real breakthrough in democratic local self-government came with the accession to office of the Left Front Government in Tripura. For the first time, elections to panchayats were held through secret ballot and with open participation of political parties. Tripura has a single-tier system of village panchayats till 1978, when the left Front Government brought forward legislation to

constitute a two-tier panchayat system. Following the 73rd Constitutional Amendment of 1992, Tripura enacted the Tripura Panchayat Act, 1993, and introduced a three tier structure. This book examines the role of women members of Gram Panchayats in Tripura since 1993, when their representation in Panchayats increased due to reservation of seats as a result of the 73rd Constitutional Amendment. This book analyzes their socio-economical and political background as well as their level of awareness about socio-political situation and their exposure to outside world. It also investigates whether their election to panchayat bodies has made any significant change in the status of women in rural areas. Further it also discusses the factors that motivated women members to plunge into politics and fight panchayat elections.

This book contains ten chapters out of which the first chapter gives us the background of Panchayati Raj in Tripura and institutionalization of Panchayat Raj happened in Tripura. In the second, third, fourth and fifth chapter the author tries to elaborate the objectives of his work, methodology used, literature review and the area of his study. In the sixth chapter entitled "Socio-Economic Profile of Panchayat Members" the author tried to analyze the profile of Gram Panchayat members in their socio-economic and political background. The seventh chapter deals with the participation, activities and achievements of gram panchayat members especially of women in the state of Tripura. In the eighth chapter "Credit for Poverty Eradication" the author tried to show how far the loan and assistance of government bodies have been able to reach the grassroots level. In the ninth chapter the author tried to highlight some of the major problems faced by women panchayat members in the Gram Panchayats

In this book the study carried out by the author indicated that the participation of women in panchayat decision-making process in term of attendance, opinion expressed and issue raised in the PR meetings, confidence repose and satisfaction for effective participation was noteworthy. They were not mere mute spectators or ornaments in the decision-making process, rather a likely force to reckon with. They maintained contacts with villagers took villagers demand into cognizance and tried to deliver whatever was possible for them. The author also found that most of women members had no previous political exposure and experience. Most of them did not hold any type of political post and even they were not primary members of any parties. But at present women have joined various socio-economic and political activities. It is also true that almost everywhere they are caught in the dilemma of role adjustment. Bias against women is likely to slow down only gradually.

In this book the author observed that women's participation in the Gram Panchayats has substantially increased but mere reservation would not solve the problem unless women

members are given due powers to function effectively. In order to empower women's he advocated all women panchayats members should be trained by suitable resource persons dealing with self-government activities. The training should include the philosophy as well as administration of panchayati raj, the political and social essence of democracy and the attitude towards the people. The training courses should address such general works and programmes which are specific to women's welfare. The training programmes should be carried out in small groups so that there is sufficient interaction between the trainer and the trainees. The author also acknowledged the fact that newly elected representatives should not be expected to acquire overnight the capabilities needed in different fields. Till they achieve such competence, they should be guided and assisted by elderly and experienced panchayat personals.

The author wants the women's dual responsibilities to be appreciated and shares by male members. He also acknowledged that the women panchayat members still face male dominance not in family but also in the official work. The author noticed that women may have some exclusive problems such as maternity and childcare but all development issues almost equally concern both men and women. Their interest cannot be isolated from the economic, social and political interest of other groups. In this book the author observed that women members unanimously asserted that they were not in favour of exclusive women's issues but rather they tried to work for collective interest of village also. Overall this book is a commendable effort by the author to asses' women's participation in Panchayati Raj Institution in Tripura. This work has revealed a lot of facts relating to the issue of political empowerment of women in the state. The distinctive approach and methodology adopted by the author have enabled him to capture the socio-economic profile of the women members in Tripura. His study also shows how energetic attempts of members made the panchayati raj institution in rural areas vibrant and lively.

Bina Rai